

**Reference letters as components of the personal tutor and career services systems:
Action research and policy formalisation**

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Citation

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Purpose

Student services such as personal tutorship, career advice and reference letters for postgraduate studies are viewed as important for the international branch campuses (IBCs) of universities seeking to justify higher tuition fees than local competitors. However, student services in IBCs have largely escaped research attention. This research examines how services can be linked to achieve improvements to student learning outcomes, encourage proactive student behaviour, and address the imbalance of students considering work experience after graduation versus those aiming to pursue immediate postgraduate studies overseas. This extended abstract of a seminar presentation is part of the Public Dissemination & Consultation Stage of a broader action research project. Reporting on this project complements the literature on the internationalisation of the higher education industry (e.g. Altbach & Knight, 2007; Bennett & Kane, 2011; Fielden, 2011). The seminar presentation in the IBC's business school focuses on reference letters, explains how feedback loops from the provision of reference letters were used in a pilot project, and provides an update on current

policy considerations. The consultation, dissemination and feedback loop approach of the overall action research project adds to the IBC’s future repertoire of managerial problem-solving behaviours.

Design/methodology/approach

I report and reflect on a three stages action research project that includes a 24-months pilot project linking three services to students (Reference Letter-system, Personal Tutor-system and Career Advice-system) at the IBC of a British university in China (Arp, 2016). The pilot project is followed by public consultation and policy formalisation stages (Figure 1). Data derive from the IBC’s ‘Student Barometer’-survey, summer placement and work experience programs, focus groups, and multiple seminars with faculty. I examine feedback loops between these stages and provide updates on the policy formalisation process at the university-level of the linkage tested in the pilot project.

Figure 1 Action Research Project ‘Linkage of Student Services’

Systems model of the action research process

Lewin, Kurt (1958: 201). *Group Decision and Social Change*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.

Findings

Currently, 73% of undergraduate students at the focal campus apply for further studies overseas, making it a 'feeder conduit' into postgraduate programmes. The data suggest that students think career advice to be lacking, and worry about reference letters. Both administrative and academic colleagues feel that they are not necessarily qualified to provide career guidance, and that students are unduly focused on obtaining reference letters. Gaining university-wide input from students, faculty members and administrative staff proves crucial in proposing policy to the Registrar, Vice-Provost Teaching & Learning and the Management Board.

The consultation process shows, for example, that some faculty members do not think it advisable to actively encourage students to gain work experience. Instead, they feel that work experience should merely be discussed as one of the options after graduation. Although this perspective is incongruent with views in the pedagogy literature and results of the pilot project, it is taken into account for the strategy implications of this research.

The policy formalisation process aims to address the need for multiple references per student, the concern among faculty members that many students 'hunt' for reference letters in their final year with little engagement in prior years, and the current imbalance of less than 25% of undergraduate students taking up work upon graduation. Here again, the consultation process shows that some faculty members feel that this is not an imbalance that needs to be addressed. That minority perspective resonates with the view expressed by many more faculty colleagues who do not see the provision of advice on postgraduate studies or careers as part of their role. All participants of the consultation process are cognisant of the societal and parental pressures on students to pursue postgraduate studies as quickly as possible.

Nevertheless, the pilot project undertaken in 2014-16 indicates good outcomes for student participants that did take up work after their undergraduate studies. Those outcomes were

utilised in subsequent stages of the pilot project, producing feedback loops. Figure 2 shows the use of feedback loops from the provision of personal tutor meetings, career guidance and reference letters in the pilot project.

Figure 2 Feedback loops in the pilot project

Implications

The study indicates strategy consequences that universities with existing IBCs and those considering such operations may wish to consider. Strategic questions flowing from this study include whether IBCs should aim to be ‘feeder conduits’ into postgraduate programmes, or develop a balanced student body. The latter would include postgraduate students with work experience. In the longer term this may be a strategic question of quantity versus quality, and of competitive mimicry versus distinctiveness (cf. Thomas, Billsberry, Ambrosini, & Barton, 2014).

The resource based view of the firm suggests that IBCs, particularly business schools, need a more heterogeneous approach that is not easily replicable if they are to outperform competitors (Thomas et al., 2014). Consequently, the convergence among competitors toward ‘feeder conduit’ education may become a new impetus for strategic divergence in select IBCs. It is argued that future growth and competitive advantage might be better achieved through distinct characteristics. Distinctive characteristics may include, for example, a reputation as ‘the university that prepares its students for successful careers without the need for / cost and delay of subsequent postgraduate studies’. Conversely, a differentiation strategy might involve taking ‘feeder conduit’ education even further and aiming to retain for subsequent postgraduate studies all undergraduate students within the university.

Research limitations

No action research is ever perfect because no action, policy or practice ever is (cf. Coffield & Edward, 2009). Accordingly, this research is limited by the dynamic, ongoing nature of action research and the specific circumstances of a single IBC case. In addition, voice and silence – that is, whether employees contribute or withhold information, ideas, views and/or concerns at work – is very relevant to this type of research (Knoll, Wegge, Unterrainer, Silva, & Jonsson, 2016). I therefore make no claims from the data about statistical validity or applicability of our case to other IBCs. Nevertheless, our project provides a rich illustration of the particular situation of IBCs that seek to justify higher tuition fees than local competitors, differentiate themselves from local and international competitors, and primarily attract students wishing to pursue postgraduate credentials overseas. Action research enables sharing of insight that can benefit practitioners in other organisation as well as the research community (Zhang, Levenson, & Crossley, 2014). While it has these inherent strengths, I also constantly reflect on the ethical dilemmas of action research (Williamson & Prosser, 2002), particularly in educational settings (e.g. Tickle, 2001).

Originality/value

The holistic provision of student services in IBCs have to date escaped research attention and, at the practical level, the present research provides insight on how the linkage of services may assist in addressing the imbalance of students aiming for postgraduate studies overseas versus those seeking to gain work experience after graduation. At a more theoretical and strategic level, this research contributes to the literature on the management of IBCs (Shams & Huisman, 2011; Wilkins & Huisman, 2012).

Keywords

International branch campus, higher education, student services, reference letter, management

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